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Operational Status of Safety and Health in Construction

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Abstract: Development ventures endure human and economic related losses because of poor safety performance. The paper aims to assess the operational status effectiveness of health and safety in Gautam Buddha Airport Upgrading Component Construction Project. The study identifies safety hazards, review of policies and safety preventive measures adopted at construction site through necessary feedback from the respondents, field visit and interview, schedule questionnaire of the personnel related to the study area followed by secondary data from the respective office of client, consultant, contractor, journal and reports. It was recorded about 140 workers had minor accidents and 15 workers had major accidents faced at construction site. In the case of employers there were 2 minor injuries faced at the site without any fatality and death at site completion of construction. There was no any fixed budget directly mentioned under the topic of safety budget. The rules and regulations were also partially implemented or not implemented at the site strictly. The disciplinary action to the workers who violet the safety rules are taken for the serious cases only. The major cause found for poor implementation of rules and regulation was lack of safety department with adequate budget and manpower at site, lack of inspection and monitoring from the government authority and lack of specific policy and plan.

Keywords: Hazards, PPE, Rules and Regulation, Accidents, Preparedness

1. Introduction

Lumbini, the birth place of Lord Gautam Buddha, which has a tremendous potential for religious tourism is about 19 kilometers away from Gautam Buddha Airport (GBA). Gautam Buddha Airport Upgrading Component (GBAUC) will encourage direct air services to Bhairahawa (Lumbini) from South Asian countries and the Project will also assist in the development of the sub-circuit linking Bhairahawa, Lumbini, Tansen–Palpa, Pokhara, Kathmandu and Chitwan.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Safety Provision in Various Acts, Documents and Organizations

Labor act 2017 is useful to make timely provisions relating to the labor welfare, facilities and creating quality work life. It focuses on working hour, wages, working condition, accident, safety and health, worker's welfare, insurance, compensation, leave and holiday, role of trade union etc.

Chapter-7 to 10, of this act has the provisions related to working hours, working condition, removal and disposal of solid waste, remuneration, leave, Provident Fund, Gratuity and insurance. Chapter-12, clause 68-83 also includes provisions related to Occupational Safety and Health such as quarter, primary health care, safety devices, works done on contract, construction tools, temporary construction sites, safety arrangements, first aid, prevention of workers health, protection of eyes, protection from chemical substance, safety against fire, fencing of hazardous machines, lifting and heavy weight, training, disputes, order for safety, safety notice and power to determine the standards etc. Chapter-20 includes provisions related to conduct and punishment. (GON, DOL, 2017).

2.2. International Federation of Consulting Engineers

International Federation of Consulting Engineers (FIDIC) 2017, Clause-6, gives the base necessities to staff, work and development wellbeing prerequisites at site. It incorporates commitment of Staff and Labor, paces of wages and states of work, people in the administration of manager, work laws, working hours (If work should be completed external ordinary workdays and working hours, the Contractor needs to pull out with this impact), offices for staff and work, wellbeing and security, temporary worker's administration, unfamiliar faculty, temporary worker's faculty, records of contract based worker's work force and gear, scattered lead, flexibly of groceries, gracefully of water, alcoholic alcohol or medications, measures against bug and irritation annoyance, arms and ammo, celebration and strict traditions, burial service plans, kid work, constrained work, business records of laborers, laborers' associations, non-separation and equivalent chance. Proviso 19 incorporate general Requirements for Insurances, Insurance for Works and Contractor's Equipment, Insurance against Injury to Persons and Damage to Property and Insurance for Contractor's Personnel. Proviso 18 incorporates "Extraordinary Events" has supplanted "Exceptional Events" (FIDIC, 2017).

2.3. Safety Provision in Public Procurement Monitoring Office

Public Procurement Monitoring Office (PPMO) enforces the Public Procurement Act, 2006 and Public Procurement Regulation, 2007. PPMO also provides the minimum requirements for staff, labor and construction safety requirements at site. In PPMO under section VII-general condition of contract includes personal protective equipment in clause-9, insurance in clause-10 and 11, safety, security and protection of environment in clause-18, approval of use of explosive, compliance with regulation & permission for blasting in clause-71 to 73 and traffic diversion in clause-75 (PPMO, 2007).

2.4. National Building Code

The purpose of National Building Code (NBC) is to regulate acceptable level of safety to construction workers and works. NBC 114:1994, Clauses 3-17 provides the minimum

construction safety requirements for workers and other employee. This code includes handling of material, first aid and health provisions , firefighting, site Preparation through hot, cold and routine work permit for activities during excavation, foundations, walls, roofs, electrical works construction, temporary works, demolition of structures, miscellaneous requirements during demolition, application of explosives, labor welfare, and safety requirements (GON, DUDBC, 1994).

2.5. Occupational Safety and Health Administration

American congress made Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) to guarantee sheltered and sound working condition for laborers and representatives by setting and upholding laws, guidelines, principles and giving preparing, schooling and consistence help. Under OSHA law, managers are answerable for giving a sheltered and sound working environment for their laborers. Word related wellbeing and wellbeing act (OSH act) was presented in 1970 with the endeavors of managers, laborers, security and wellbeing experts, associations and backers which help for improving work environment security, lessening business related demise and wounds significantly by in excess of 65 percent. Authorization of OSH act, OSHA law and principles has a significant influence in OSHA's endeavors to diminish working environment wounds, sicknesses and fatalities. On the off chance that OSHA finds that the businesses neglect to maintain their wellbeing and wellbeing obligations, the organization takes solid unequivocal activities (US, 2014).

3. Empirical Review

Based in study directed in Head race Tunnel development at Middle Bhotekoshi, by Lama et al. (2019), Noise, vibrations were the major actual dangers, synthetic spills and concrete/silica/sand dust as significant compound peril, tumble from working stage, elusive, rock sliding, hit by total, as major mechanical risk and employment disappointment, work weakness were noted as major psychosocial risk at burrow. The significant dangers because of word related perils were distinguished as back agony, wrist torment, hearing misfortune, eye strain, skin hypersensitivity, irrigative, destructive. Sign and signals, safety policy, orientation/ awareness, safety meeting and housekeeping were used as preventive measures at Tunnel construction. Main contributing factors to reduce the risk of accident and illness were concluded as following safe working practices and improving working conditions for workers.

It likewise delineates Education and preparing for laborers and administrators is a fundamental piece of any push to forestall wounds and illness. Preparing about safe work practices and techniques have been given in numerous nations by certain organizations and worker's guilds. These strategies incorporate lockout and tag out of electrical force sources during upkeep methods, utilization of cords while working at statures, shoring

channels, giving safe strolling surfaces, etc. Execution or involved preparing, exhibiting that one knows safe practices, is vastly improved for imparting safe conduct than study hall guidance and composed assessment. Likewise, a contextual analysis on Risk Assessment of Gautam Buddha International Airport by Shakya and Mishra (2019), out of six elements huge with four factors profoundly critical (specifically Unsafe Working conditions, Safety Issue of Technical Persons, Inadequate Physical offices of Site Staff and Inadequate Budget for Safety).

4. Methodology

Gautam Buddha Airport (GBA) is located in Bhairahawa, the mid-western region of Nepal at four kilometers from the district headquarters, Rupandehi, at an altitude of 109 meters above sea level. The commencement date of GBAUC was from December 31st, 2014 and intended to complete on December 30th, 2019. The upgraded new runway is 3,000 x 45m with improvements in services facilities and terminal buildings for both International and Domestic uses for landing of ICAO 4E standard aircrafts.

In this study, the population means all the personnel of Client, Consultant and contractor (Engineers/Supervisors) and the contractor Workers involved in the construction of GBAUC in day shift. The workers were selected on the basis of their regularity and years of work experience with airport. 2 types of respondents are considered in this study. The first respondents are the Contractor, Engineer and Supervisor in the GBAUC and they performed at the projects during the last 2 years. The second type of respondents is workers and executed the construction project works from last 1 and 1/2 years. The first respondents were all 20 out of 20 assessed for the questionnaires but the second respondents were only surveyed for 42 workers out of 70 because of the large population and some of the labors were working at night.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Common Physical Hazards Prevailing in Airport Construction

Table 1 shows that 90% employers and 91% workers responded that Cut & scratch due to tools & equipment was the leading physical hazard at the Gautam Buddha airport upgradation. About 75% employers and 74% workers responded that step on the sharp or pointed objects was the second most common physical hazards in the airport construction. But 25% employers and 60% workers responded that electric shock was the third most leading physical hazard in the airport construction. And the least was caught in or between objects which was 25% and 31% responded from the employers and workers respectively.

Table 1: The most common physical hazards

		Employers		Workers	
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Most common Physical Hazards	Electric Shock	5	25%	25	60%
	Caught in or between objects	5	25%	13	31%
	Cut & scratch due to tools & equipment	18	90%	38	91%
	Step on sharp or pointed objects	15	75%	31	74%

5.2. Housekeeping Situation at Site

Table 2 shows the result of housekeeping situation at site. 69% workers responded the site was kept clean and tidy where as 26% workers responded the site was only sometimes cleaned which was major housekeeping maintained at site. In the case of Basic hygiene 65% workers responded always and 33% workers responded sometimes. Next 40% workers responded the working floor was always kept safe with no any debris and stock pile of material on the floor and the rest 60% workers responded the working floor was sometimes maintained safe. The least housekeeping maintained was the proper waste disposal for that 40% workers responded there was proper waste disposal at site and 58% workers responded sometimes the waste product were disposed.

Table 2: Housekeeping condition at site

Housekeeping situation at Site	Workers					
	Always		Sometimes		No	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Site tidiness	29	69%	11	26%	2	5%
Basic Hygiene	27	65%	14	33%	1	2%
Proper Waste Disposal	17	40%	24	58%	1	2%
Safe Working Floor	17	40%	25	60%	0	0%

As visited the site, it was found that the site was being cleaning but the work floor was full of water as it seem that the wall plaster was being water cured. The waste product from the construction site was found to be burnt at one corner away from work site. The waste product from the toilet was connected to the septic tank. Housekeeping is pivotal to safe work environments. It can help forestall wounds and improve efficiency and spirit, just as establish a decent first connection with guests. Each laborer should assume a function in housekeeping, regardless of whether that implies keeping their own workspace clean. Housekeeping ought to be a progressing cycle, not a one-time practice.

5.3. Common Mechanical Hazards

Similarly, 75% employers and 55% workers responded that fall was the leading mechanical hazard at the Gautam Buddha airport construction site. And 25% employers and 45% workers responded that slip as the least mechanical hazard at construction site. Working Floors (slippery/uneven), Vehicles/Equipments, Working locations, Hand tools and Obstacles/entanglement are common mechanical hazard. Silimar to Mishra and Sharestha (2017) as situational characteristics could not be assessed accurately and during KII also, Safety was not in supervisors first priority. In this way predisposition characteristics i.e susceptibility of people, perceptions and environmental forces and situational characteristics i.e risk assessment by individuals (like no proper and suitable PPE), peer pressure, priorities of supervisor (project was behind the schedule) and attitude are causing for accident as Epidemiological theory.

5.4. Welfare Amenities

According to Table 3, 95% employers and 98% workers responded that they were always provided safe drinking water and 5% employers and 2% workers responded they were sometimes provided by the safe drinking water.90% employers and 95% workers responded that there were always been provided with toilet facilities and 5% employers and 2.5% workers responded there were sometimes been provided with toilet facilities besides that 2.5% workers responded that there were no any toilet facilities.

Table 3: Welfare amenities provided at site

		Employers						Workers					
		Always	Percentage	Sometimes	Percentage	No	Percentage	Always	Percentage	Sometimes	Percentage	No	Percentage
Welfare amenities	Safe drinking water	19	95%	1	5%	0	0%	41	98%	1	2%	0	0%
	Toilet facility	18	90%	1	5%	1	5%	40	95%	1	2.5%	1	2.5%
	Separate toilet for male and female	12	60%	4	20%	4	20%	23	55%	2	5%	17	40%
	Arrangement of living Accommodation	16	80%	1	5%	3	15%	28	67%	12	28%	2	5%
	Provision for Canteen	17	85%	0	0%	3	15%	42	100%	0	0%	0	0%
	Separate changing room for male and female	2	10%	3	15%	15	75%	0	0%	7	17%	35	83%

Drinking water was directly fetched from deep bore but as per the senior lab technician of construction site the water quality was tested from the Shankarnagar Water Experiment Laboratory near to Butwal. Distance between drinking water storage and toilet were not properly maintained that can cause contamination of the drinking water. Latrine and washroom was not slick and clean which is by all accounts inclined of bacterial just as viral defilement and can prompt transmittable infections. There is a high possibility of natural perils. Separate toilet for male and female was made on the site but it seems that the workers were not aware of the separation and used by both male and female.

5.5. Compensation for Disabled Workers

Figure 4 shows provision of compensation for the disabled workers working at Gautam Buddha Airport construction site. About 98% workers responded there was no any person being disabled due to accident at work but 2% that is 1 worker responded there was a person being disabled (right thumb was cut while using the saw machine) due to the accident at site. In the case of workers being disabled or death occurred at site 90% workers responded the contractor pay compensation to the workers and 10% workers responded the Insurance Company will provide the compensation to the disabled workers.

Table 4: Compensation for disabled workers

		Workers	
		Number	Percentage
Any Person Being Disabled Due To Accident While At Work	Yes	1	2%
	No	41	98%
Worker Becomes Disabled Or Death Occurred At Site, Who Provides Compensation	Government	0	0%
	Employer	0	0%
	Contractor	38	90%
	Insurance	4	10%

According to KII, there was a person whose right thumb was cut while using the saw machine but he was operated and the thumb was fixed and the victim was paid all the medical expenses by the contractor and also paid the extra 3 month salary as compensation and told the worker to rest at his home. He also said that still now the contractor has not claimed for the compensation against the accident to the insurance company.

5.6. Safety Practice Adopted

Safety Practice Adopted has been analyzed based on Workers Welfare at Construction Site and Accident Causes along with Status of Accidents.

5.7. Working Condition

Figure 1 shows that, 69% workers were used to work for 8 hours in a day where as 31% workers responded to work 10 hours in a day. And the refreshing hours during the

working hours was mostly 1 hour which was responded by 60% workers, 10% workers responded they only got 30 minutes refreshing hours in a working days, 29% workers responded they had to work on the rotation basis and 2% workers responded they did not got any refreshing hours during the whole working hours. Next 74% workers responded they had to work for whole 7 days in a week and only 26% workers responded that they used to get 1 day leave in a week. Besides that 36% workers responded that they used to work at night and 64% workers responded they do not used to work at night. The good thing was there was no any child labor at the construction of Gautam Buddha Airport.

Figure 1: Working statuses at site

According to section 8-Particular Condition of contract, it is clear mentioned that the normal working hours is 8 hrs in normal case and 6 days in a week. But according to KII to complete the major works like mass concrete at apron and asphalt work in runway the work need to work for the over time. This was obvious but rotation among worker should be maintained in a way that same labour could not be overloaded and refreshment break maximum at 5 hrs was suggested by labour Act 2017 should be enforced.

5.8. Workers Remuneration

The equal remuneration to male and female engaged in the same nature of work without any discrimination. About 90% employers and 67% workers responded that the both male and female workers got equal remuneration for the same nature of work without any discrimination. But 10% employers and 33% workers responded that they did not get equal remuneration. This difference was caused depending upon labour contractor commission deployed. So, Minimum wages should be assured by the project team to labour directly besides labour contractor commission.

5.9. Workers Remuneration of Workers as per Government of Nepal

The employers at the site were asked if they were paying remuneration to the workers as per Government of Nepal standard and about 90% employers responded that the workers were being paid minimum remuneration as per Government of Nepal standard.

5.10. Wages for Over Time

All the workers used to work for the over time besides the normal working hours among them 60% workers responded they worked for less than four hours and get their wages according to normal per hour rate. 21% workers responded they had to work for four hours extra over time and 19% worker responded that they had to work for more than 4 hours and were paid according to the hours worked at site. Mostly, it founds to argued to pay more for overtime.

5.11. Provision of Welfare Fund

It was found that the employers did not provide any kind of welfare fund for the interest and welfare activities of the workers. The researcher questioned that if there were any welfare fund for immediate financial assistance for workers, providing education to workers or employer or their children, making arrangement for sports and entertainment and in case of emergency situation like natural calamities but all the workers responded negative towards welfare.

5.12. Provision of Compensation against Accident

As per the questionnaire asked to the workers about the compensation provision against accident then 98% workers responded there was no compensation against accident and only 2% worker responded there was provision of compensation against accident.

5.13. Accident Occurred in Gautam Buddha Airport Site

About 90% workers and 65% employers responded that accident occurred in their site during work but about 10% workers and 35% employers responded that there was no accident occurred at site. According to Health Officer and KII it was found out that many accidents were occurred during the construction of Terminal Buildings works and Road works. Accident reporting was done though no notice and awareness were found to be circulated at site effectively.

5.14. Types of Accident Occurred at Site

Table 5 shows the result of accident happening at site. 81% workers responded that there were minor accident occurred in the site but 19% workers responded that there were major injuries occurred at site.

Table 5: Types of accident occurred at site

Types of accidents	Workers	
	Numbers	Percentage
Minor	34	81%
Major	8	19%
Fatal	0	0%

Table 6: The most common accidents recorded at the site

Nature of accidents	Workers		Employers	
	Minor	Major	Minor	Major
Cut and scratch	65	2		
Eye infection	35			
Fracture	30	10	2	
Back pain	10			
Dog Bite		2		
Snake Bite		1		
Total	140	15	2	0

Plate 1: Installation of heavy Truss work at International Terminal Building

Plate 1 shows the installation of the heavy metal truss at International Terminal Building. The workers working for the work were experienced and quite courageous and they belong from our neighboring country India. It was found that the workers used to hook up the safety belt to a rope tied up with the column of the main structure.

Plate 2: Installation of composite roofing system at International Terminal Building

Plate 2 shows the installation of the composite roofing system at International Terminal Building. The roofing system has 6 layers and they had started to install the first layer. According to the installation team the first layer was the risky layers for them because they had stand on the purlin of the truss and lay their Galvalume liner sheet.

5.15. Personal Protective Equipment to workers

88% employers responded that the Personal Protective Equipment was provided to workers as per need and nature of the work. 6% employers responded the PPE was always provided to the workers and the rest 6% employers responded the PPE was often provided to the workers at the construction site.

5.16. Preventive Measures of Accident Prevention

Table 7 highlights the preventive measures used to prevent accidents at site. 95% workers and 95% employers responded sign and signals were used to prevent accidents but among them some replied sign and signals were only used to some extent and it is the leading preventive measure used at site. The material storing was the second leading preventive measure and 83% workers responded positive towards material storing. 29% workers and 15% employers responded there was emergency exit at the construction site but 71% workers and 85% employers responded there was no any emergency exit to prevent accident.

Table 7: Preventive measures used to prevent accident

Preventive Measures	Workers						Employers					
	Yes	Percentage	Sometimes	Percentage	No	Percentage	Yes	Percentage	Sometimes	Percentage	No	Percentage
Sign and signals	16	38%	24	57%	2	5%	8	40%	11	55%	1	5%
Emergency Exit	12	29%	-	-	30	71%	3	15%	-	-	17	85%
Training	6	14%	-	-	36	86%	15	75%	-	-	5	25%
Material storing	35	83%	-	-	7	17%	-	-	-	-	-	-

It was observed that most of the sign and signals were dimmed and not clearly visible with wear and tear at corners. According the KII, the site is big and more open areas are available so there was no any emergency exit and in the case of any emergency the apron area at the airside and car parking at the landside can be used as assembly point. In the case of safety training the safety incharge used to provide training to all the new recruited workers at a time before rushed towards the work. The materials are stored at different stores for different materials. According to store incharge there was cement godown, rebar yard, plywood store, river gravel yards, bitumen yards, and the small accessories was stored at the store office site made near at the site.

Figure 2: Control Measures used to control accidents

As per the site observation it was found that only at the control tower which was 8 storeys with basement was netted with the safety net on the outer periphery and other building were only scaffold without safety net. The guardrails and barriers were provided at the dangerous areas like staircase, excavated areas, equipment yards etc. It was also observed

that there was only one fire extinguisher which was hanged at the outer wall of the engineering office. As per KII in the case of fire firefighting the existing airport has the firefighting vehicles which can be used in the case of emergency.

5.17. Availability of Safety Engineer/Officer and Medical Person

Exactly 100% employers and about 81% workers responded safety officer was available at site. Regarding the safety department 60% employers responded there was the working station along with the department at the construction site for regular inspection of the risky works. Exactly 100% workers and 100% employers responded that Medical person was available at site.

5.18. Reporting of Accidents

Table 8 shows the result of reporting of accidents to the higher authority. 93% workers responded the accidents were informed to the management team and 65% employers responded that the accidents were reported to the labor office. Only 7% workers responded the accidents were not reported to the management team but 35% employers responded the accident was not reported to the labor office. Among the responses from the workers and employers 74% workers responded major accidents and 26% workers responded all kind of accidents were reported to the management team. Among the employers who were positive towards reporting, 62% employers responded they report all types of accidents to the labor office and 38% employers responded only major accidents were reported.

Table 8: Reporting of Accidents

		Workers		Employers	
Do accidents reported to management team and labor office	Yes	39	93%	13	65%
	No	3	7%	7	35%
Degree of accident reported	Major	29	74%	5	38%
	Minor	0	0%	0	0%
	All	10	26%	8	62%

According to the medical person, she replied that a person positioned as Social Mobilizer from the government authority visit the site every month and collect all the data related to the accidents occurred at the Gautam Buddha Airport construction site.

5.19. Safety Training

65% employers responded that safety training was conducted only once at a project at the starting. 25% employers responded the safety training was conducted every year and about 10% employers responded the safety training was conducted every month. As per the site safety supervisor, the safety training was neither conducted yearly, monthly nor weekly. He replied, at the time of new workers recruited at site for any new work he used to call the new workers and provide some safety related speech. As per KII, in volume 2, item

No.5 under section N (FAT, Training & Commissioning) of the contract document there are some fund related to training but that amount was only for 12 CAAN Electrical persons for operational purpose. As referred in literature section, Quest (2015) highlighted the need of training in construction industry of Nepal.

5.20. Safety Inspection

Table 9 illustrates the safety inspection from different authority of Nepal Government at construction site. Only 2% workers and 45% employers responded there was daily safety inspection by the project manager at site. About 43% workers and 15% employers responded there was safety inspection once a week. An almost equal response that is 33% workers and 35% employer's responded inspection was done on the monthly basis. Next 35% employers and null workers responded there was safety inspection from the government authority. But 81% workers and 65% employers responded there was no any safety inspection from higher authority and 19% workers responded safety inspection was done sometimes. Out of the responses from the safety inspection from the government authority, 50% workers and 43% employers replied inspection done by the labor department and 50% workers and 57% employers replied from other department which was indicated to the higher authority of CAAN itself and ADB.

Table 9: Safety Inspection at Site

		Workers		Employers	
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Safety inspection by Project manager or site engineer	Daily	1	2%	9	45%
	Twice a week	0	0%	1	5%
	Once a week	18	43%	3	15%
	Monthly	14	33%	7	35%
	Never	8	21%	0	0%
Safety inspection from government authority	Yes	0	0%	7	35%
	No	34	81%	13	65%
	Sometimes	8	19%	0	0%
Inspected Authority	Labor Department	4	9.5%	3	15%
	DUDBC	0	0%	0	0%
	Municipality	0	0%	0	0%
	Others	4	9.5%	4	20%
Safety checklist before starting the work	Yes	1	2%		
	No	26	62%		
	Sometimes	15	36%		

5.21. Implementation of Rules and Regulations at Site

Exactly none of the respondents replied that the rules and regulations were always implemented at the construction site. Rather 69% workers and 70% employers responded

only partially the rules and regulations are implemented at the site and the rest responded rules and regulations are never implemented at site.

5.22. Sufficiency of Existing Laws, Acts and Regulation against Health and Safety

In the context of Nepal there are many Acts and Regulations which can be some listed as Labor Act (1992), revised on (2017), International Federation of Consulting Engineers (FIDIC) harmonized edition (2010), Public Procurement Monitoring Office (PPMO) (2007), National Building Code (NBC) (1994), Health and Safety at Work etc. and Act (1974), etc. These all Acts and Regulations talk about the health and safety at the construction industries.

5.23. Safety Budget

Table 10 shows the result of allocation of Safety budget at construction site. 20% of Client/Consultant and 53% employers responded that there was safety budget allocated. 60% Client/Consultant and 27% employers responded that there was no any safety budget allocated for the site. And, 20% client/consultant and 20% employer responded that there were unaware of safety budget allocated.

Table 10: Allocation of safety Budget

Allocation of safety Budget	Client/Consultant		Employers	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Yes	1	20%	8	53%
No	3	60%	4	27%
Don't Know	1	20%	3	20%

After studying the contract document it has been revealed that there is no any fixed budget directly mentioned under the topic of safety budget. But there is mentioned indirectly about it. Contract document talks about provision Health and Safety Plan which includes Medical officer, safety manager, and their respective supervisors. It has also the provision of emergency preparedness and response plan, first aid training, first aid supplies including different accessories required, Safety, health and welfare for labors, safety of public, Safety notices, sign and information notice boards, Fire protection and firefighting equipment, Management of epidemic and hazardous materials, Vermin, pest and mosquito control. All these are not free of cost and need definitely some budgets.

6. Conclusion

Electric shock, caught in or between objects, cut & scratch due to tools & equipment and step on sharp or pointed objects were some of the most common physical hazards found at Gautam Buddha Airport Upgrading Component and among that Cut & scratch due to tools & equipment was the leading physical hazard and step on the sharp or pointed objects was

the second. Next fall was the leading mechanical hazard and slip as the least mechanical hazard at construction site. The chapter 4.1 illustrates the occupational hazards at GBAUC. Although the normal working hours is 8 hrs in normal case and 6 days in a week but to complete the major works like mass concrete at apron and asphalt work in runway the work need to work for the over time. For that 90% employers and 67% workers responded that the both male and female workers got equal remuneration for the same nature of work without any discrimination and were being paid minimum remuneration as per Government of Nepal standard.

Deep bore was source of drinking water after water quality test. Latrine and restroom was not slick and clean which is by all accounts inclined of bacterial just as viral pollution. Living accommodation was not clean and spitted all over the wall which can also lead to communicable diseases. The canteen premises were neat and clean with good and hygienic foods. There was no separate changing room for male and female as it was seen that the workers quarter was inside the construction site. According to Health Officer and KII it was found out that many accidents were occurred during the construction of Terminal Buildings works and Road works. It was recorded about 140 workers had minor accidents and 15 workers had major accidents faced at construction site. In the case of employers there were 2 minor injuries faced at the site. The major thing was no any fatality and death at site till date. These accidents were also reported to Social Mobilizer from the government authority every month. About 90% employers during works in airport construction responded that contractor had the leading responsible role for the accident at site. The details for Accident and Major Causes are reflected in chapter 4.3.

Sign and signals, safety policy, orientation/ awareness, safety training, safety inspection, maintenance of plant, tools & equipment and housekeeping were used as preventive measures. Safety nets, guardrails and barrier and firefighting equipment were the Control Measures used to Control Accident. PPE were provided but not sufficient and safety helmet was found to be leading PPE provided to the workers. Main contributing factors to reduce the accident and illness were concluded as following safe working practices and improving working conditions for workers. Most of the workers did not know about the provision of Labor Act. The Rules and Regulations were also partially implemented or not implemented at the site strictly. The disciplinary action to the workers who violet the safety rules were taken for the serious cases only. The major cause found for poor implementation of rules and regulation was lack of safety department with adequate budget and manpower at site, lack of inspection and monitoring from the government authority and lack of specific policy and plan. There were no practices of medical examination to the workers. No medical doctor recruited at site although there is provision in contract document. Only staff nurse was recruited.

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